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ANALYSIS OF TEST RESULTS OF A HOUSEHOLD ABSORPTION REFRIGERATING APPLIANCE ON AN ELECTRIC AND GAS SOURCE OF THERMAL ENERGY

One of the biggest challenges for refrigeration systems is their conversion to environmentally friendly refrigerants. This attracts the attention of developers of household refrigeration equipment to absorption refrigeration devices (ARD), which include an absorption refrigeration unit (ARU). ARD working fluid consists of natural components – ammonia water solution with the addition of an inert gas (hydrogen). Therefore, the use of ARU can be considered as one of the options for transferring to environmentally friendly refrigerants. In recent years, in connection with the rapidly developing gasification of the population of Europe, an alternative has arisen – the operation of household ARD on natural gas. Natural gas can become an alternative to electrical energy in stationary operating conditions of household refrigeration appliances. Thus, the object of the study was a single-chamber household refrigerator with a low-temperature compartment «Kiev-410» (Ukraine).

In this paper, the study is aimed at comparing the thermal modes of operation and the costs of operating a household ARD on electric energy and natural gas. To solve this, it was necessary to determine the temperatures at the characteristic points of the refrigeration apparatus and in the chamber, as well as the energy consumption of the absorption-type apparatus in accordance with regulatory documents, at various values of the thermal load on the thermosyphon and various ambient temperatures.

The studies were carried out at elevated outdoor temperatures: 28–33 °C. The range of thermal loads on the ARU thermosyphon electric heater was 50–130 W. The range of numerical values of natural gas consumption in the burner was $(2.8–8.8) \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. In the process of conducting experimental studies of household ARD, results were obtained showing the economic prospects of working in stationary conditions on natural gas.

At the same time, ARD of increased useful volume (200 dm³ and above) has the greatest prospects. The daily operating costs in them are 0.078...0.084 USD, which is 23...27 % lower than the case of using electricity. When the ARU thermosyphon is built into the heating and hot water supply system, it becomes possible to use the temperature potential of the waste products of combustion and completely eliminate operating costs.

Keywords: refrigeration equipment, absorption refrigeration unit, environmentally friendly refrigerants, heat recovery.

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1. Introduction

The transfer of refrigeration systems to environmentally friendly refrigerants attracts the attention of developers of household refrigeration equipment and to absorption refrigeration devices (ARD), which include an absorption refrigeration unit (ARU) [1]. ARU working fluid consists of natural components – ammonia water solution with the addition of an inert gas (hydrogen) [2]. Therefore, the use of ARD can be considered as one of the options for transferring to environmentally friendly refrigerants.

ARD have a number of such positive qualities as noiselessness, reliability and long service life, absence of vibration, magnetic and electric fields during operation, the ability to use several energy sources in one unit – both electrical and thermal [3, 4]. ARDs are practically insensitive to changes in the parameters of the current in the network in the voltage range 160–240 V [5].

The advantages of ARD should be attributed to the lower, in comparison with compression analogs, the cost, which in many cases is of decisive importance. ARD are effective when used as mini-refrigerators, minibars, in built-in

and transport models of refrigerators, when the refrigerating capacity does not exceed 20 W and it is impractical to use compression refrigeration machines [6].

At the same time, ARD have an increased energy consumption in comparison with similar compression models, which limits their area of application and market share in household refrigeration equipment.

For this reason, works aimed at increasing the energy efficiency of ARD are relevant.

It is also important in modern conditions that the ARU working fluid – ammonia-water solution with the addition of an inert gas (hydrogen, helium or their mixture [7]) belongs to natural refrigerants. It is absolutely environmentally safe, since it has zero values of the ozone-depleting potential and the potential for the «greenhouse» effect [2].

ARDs also have a number of such unique qualities as [5, 8, 9]:

a) possibility of using several different sources of thermal energy in one apparatus – both electrical and alternative (heat of combustion of fossil fuel and biogas, solar radiation, exhaust gases of internal combustion engines);

b) ability to work with low-quality energy sources, including electrical in the range of network voltage from 160 to 240 V;

c) noiselessness, high reliability and long service life.

ARD equipped with burners are widely used by tourists and travelers, as there is no alternative to them in areas with a lack of electricity.

The advantages of ARD include the minimum cost among the existing types of refrigeration equipment of low refrigeration capacity, which in many cases determines their popularity among users.

In recent years, in connection with the rapidly developing gasification of the population of Europe, an alternative has arisen – the operation of household ARD on natural gas. And if devices operating on liquefied gas (propane) or kerosene are widely known on the market for household absorption refrigeration equipment, then the use of natural gas as a source of thermal energy has not yet been practiced. Natural gas can become an alternative to electric energy in stationary conditions of operation of household refrigeration appliances, especially in the presence of economic preferences.

The aim of this research is to compare the thermal modes of operation and the costs of operating a household AHP using electric energy and natural gas.

So, *the object of research* was a single-chamber household refrigerator with a low-temperature compartment «Kiev-410» (Ukraine).

2. Methods of research

When choosing the object of research, let's guide by the following consideration, the temperature and energy characteristics of the ARD and the influence on them of operating parameters and structural elements should be of both scientific and practical interest.

ARD manufactured at the Vasilkiv Refrigerator Plant (Ukraine) using serial technologies meets these requirements: this is a household single-chamber refrigerator with a low-temperature compartment (NLTC) «Kiev-410» AIII-160 (Fig. 1, Table 1) [10]. According to the normative document [11], the temperature is maintained in the LTC not higher than minus 18 °C, and in the RC – in the range of 0–5 °C.

Fig. 1. Overall dimensions of the ASH-160 «Kiev-410» absorption refrigerating device with a low-temperature compartment: *a* – front view; *b* – side view

The main characteristics of the research object

Table 1

Model	Useful volume, dm ³		Overall dimensions, m			Distinctive design features
	general	LTC	width	depth	height	
ASH-160 «Kiev-410» absorption single-chamber refrigerator with LTC	160	14	0.58	0.65	1.03	The vertical evaporator is installed in a heat-insulated block in the opening of the rear wall of the cabinet

To solve this aim, it is necessary to determine:

- temperatures at characteristic points of the refrigeration apparatus and in the chamber;
- the amount of energy consumption of absorption-type devices in accordance with the regulatory documents [12], at different values of the thermal load on the thermosyphon (Q) and at different ambient temperatures.

The experimental setup contains a system for measuring and recording temperatures, a system for supplying, stabilizing and measuring electrical power, a system for supplying and measuring the flow rate of natural gas, and a sample of the refrigeration apparatus under study.

The experimental device is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Diagram of the experimental device:

- heat-insulated body of the refrigerating device;
- absorption refrigeration unit;
- adjustable autotransformer;
- voltage stabilizer;
- measuring complex;
- electric power meter;
- thermocouples;
- temperature measuring device;
- natural gas flow meter;
- gas main;
- gas flow regulator

The research object consists of a thermally insulated body 1 with ARU on the back wall 2.

The ARU electric heater is connected to a system for supplying, regulating, stabilizing and measuring electrical power.

The supply of electric power to the regulator 3, which is used as an adjustable autotransformer of the LATR type (Ukraine), is carried out through the voltage stabilizer LVT ASN-250 (Ukraine) 4. The electric load is registered using the measuring complex K-50 (Ukraine) 5, and the electric power – counter TurBZ-2 (Bulgaria) 6.

For operation on natural gas, a burner device was used, consisting of a standard sleeve for an electric heater, welded to the body of the ARU thermosyphon and a chimney. The chimney served to remove the combustion products and ran parallel to the vertical section of the ARU reflux condenser.

In the lower part of the sleeve, a heat source was installed – the flame of a gas burner.

The consumption of natural gas network was measured using a standard S6RL gas meter (Ukraine).

The temperatures at the characteristic points of the LTC and RC were measured using standard chromel-copel thermocouples 7. The thermocouples are switched through a recording device, which was a SH300 digital voltmeter (Ukraine) 8.

3. Research results and discussion

The results of experimental studies are presented in the form of graphical dependencies in Fig. 3, 4.

Fig. 3. Dependence of the thermal conditions of the Ash-160 «Kyev-410» refrigerator on the magnitude of the heat load of the electric heater: *a* – temperature difference between the environment and the temperatures in the chambers; *b* – average rate of change in the temperature difference over time; ● – low-temperature compartment; ◆ – refrigerating chamber

The studies were carried out at elevated outdoor temperatures: 28–33 °C. Under these conditions, according to the normative document [12], the operating mode of the ARD is continuous 1, that is, with a constant supply of heat load to the ARU thermosyphon.

The range of thermal loads on the ARU thermosyphon electric heater was 50–130 W. The range of numerical values of natural gas consumption in the burner was $2.8\text{--}8.8 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$.

Fig. 3, *b*, Fig. 4, *b* shows the average rate of change in the temperature difference over time. This indicator characterizes the intensity of the cooling process of the chambers of the research object.

In the LTC, the maximum cooling intensity took place in the range of heat loads of the electric heater of 50–110 W, which is confirmed by the results of other works [13, 14].

Fig. 4. Dependence of the thermal regimes of the ASh-160 «Kyev-410» refrigerator on the numerical values of the natural gas consumption: *a* – the temperature difference between the environment and the temperatures in the chambers; *b* – the average rate of change in the temperature difference over time; ● – low-temperature compartment; ◆ – refrigerating chamber

In the RC, the intensity of the cooling process is linear over the entire range of heat loads of the heater 50–130 W. The increase in the upper value of the thermal load of the thermosyphon can be explained by the margin of the heat exchange surface of the evaporator set in the RC.

When the AHP was running on natural gas in the LHC, the maximum cooling intensity took place in the flow rate range of $2.8\text{--}6.0 \cdot 10^6$ m³/s.

In the HC, the intensity of the cooling process was also linear over the entire flow rate range $2.8\text{--}8.8 \cdot 10^6$ m³/s. And, accordingly, the increase in the upper value of the thermal load of the thermosyphon is also explained by the margin of the heat exchange surface of the evaporator set in the HC.

It is advisable to evaluate the economic part for the maximum values of the refrigerating capacity of the research object.

So, with a heat load of an electric heater of 110 W, its daily power consumption will be 2.64 kW·h.

With a natural gas consumption of $6.0 \cdot 10^6$ m³/s per second, its daily consumption will be 0.5184 m³.

For the current pricing policy for energy resources in Ukraine in May 2021 – 1 kW·h costs 0.062 USD, and 1 m³ of natural gas – 0.315 USD, the daily cost of operating ARD will be 0.164 USD (for electricity) and 0.163 USD (for natural gas).

It is necessary to remember that the above results are based on operating conditions at elevated outdoor temperatures. When the object of research is operated in the temperature range of 22–25 °C and there is an automatic control system, its daily power consumption

is 1.63 kW·h [5]. In this case, the daily operating cost would be 0.101 USD.

Taking into account the thermal potential of natural gas (heat of combustion 31.8 MJ/m³ [15]), the average daily heat load on the ARU generator in our studies was 191 W.

Recent studies [16] have shown that the optimal heat load of our research object in the presence of a control system is 75–80 W. In this regard, it is possible to predict the parameters of the daily cost of operating ARD on natural gas, about 0.111 USD.

The results obtained characterize the technical and cost parameters of household AHP of the average volume of cooling chambers (120...160 dm³). For chambers of increased volume (200 dm³ and above), when there are practically no restrictions on the mass and size characteristics of the ARU [17], it is possible to reduce gas energy consumption by 1.2...1.3 times by using regenerative heat exchangers [18].

In the case of mini-refrigerators with high requirements for weight and size characteristics, one should expect an increased gas consumption by a factor of 2.1...2.6 [18].

It should also be noted that the temperature of the combustion products at the level of 250...350 °C is sufficient for the ARU operation [19]. The theoretical temperature of natural combustion with an average value of excess air of 1.0 is 2050 °C [20], and in practice, on average, 1200 °C [21].

In this regard, it is advisable to embed ARD into the heating or hot water supply system of the house, which will additionally solve the problems of refrigerated storage of food products. In such a scheme, the ARD will operate in the mode of heat recovery from hot combustion products, i. e. there will be no operating costs.

Thus, the studies carried out have shown that:

- of all types of household refrigeration equipment of the absorption type, the maximum economic benefits when operating on natural gas can be obtained for chambers of increased usable volume (200 dm³ and above);
- the cost of operating chambers with ARU of average volume (120...160 dm³) is commensurate both for the case of using electric energy and natural gas;
- from an economic point of view, natural gas should not be used for absorption refrigerators of small useful volume (30...50 dm³).

4. Conclusions

In the process of conducting experimental studies of household ARD, results were obtained showing the economic prospects of working in stationary conditions on natural gas.

At the same time, ARD of increased useful volume (200 dm³ and above) has the greatest prospects. The daily operating costs in them are 0.078...0.084 USD, which is 23...27 % lower than the case of using electricity.

When the ARU thermosyphon is built into the heating and hot water supply system, it becomes possible to use the temperature potential of the waste products of combustion and completely eliminate operating costs.

At the same time, there remains the potential for further thermal engineering improvement of the gas burner device, for example, with the help of a turbulizer for the flow of hot combustion products [17].

An important fact is the possibility of working with a household ARD both with an electric power source and

with natural gas. This improves the reliability of the refrigeration appliance, especially in areas with problematic power supply.

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